

FRENCH GRAMMAR AND ITS THEORY.

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Abstract: *Grammar is defined as the branch of linguistics that studies the laws of change and combination of words to form meaningful ideas.*

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Grammar is divided into morphology and syntax. Morphology is the study of grammatical morphemes and the meanings expressed by them, while syntax is the study of sentence structure.

The main element of grammar - grammatical category - consists of proportionality of form and content. Its content is manifested in two or more oppositions. In form, it is expressed in word change or the use of auxiliary words, word order or intonation in a sentence.

From the point of view of existence, the grammatical category is semantic, that is, normative and asemantic. Asemantic categories perform only a structural-organizing function. Semantic category is primary, asemantic use of grammatical forms is secondary and it occurs only under certain conditions.

The essence of the dialectical approach to the facts of the language is manifested in the fact that grammatical categories and meanings can be interconnected and overlap, always assume that grammar is related to other aspects of the language, and pay attention to intermediate events in grammatical construction [1,5].

Grammatical meaning core is a concept that reflects properties or relations of objects. Linguistic form represents the element of language in general, with all its aspects. However, in a certain situation, different aspects of the event may be reflected. As a result, the appropriate grammatical form discovers the subtlety of meaning in communication.

During communication, people use both clear and vague concepts. This, in turn, leads to a narrowing, change, neutralization of the grammatical category, and syncretism.

The language system is not a fixed thing, so it contains many transient phenomena that occupy an intermediate position in different categories.

Due to the activity of the language system, the meanings of grammatical phenomena are refined, and as a result, objective difficulties arise in establishing classification boundaries between them. This is precisely the objective reason for the emergence of different theoretical analysis methods that reflect different aspects of the same phenomenon. In nature, there are no demarcation lines that can be applied equally to all situations.

This situation is the reason why scientists often ignore grammar even in fundamental concepts such as words and phrases, clauses. Because it seemed impossible to give them a definition that would cover all cases.

There is no need to abandon certain notions of grammar: the dialectical nature of the grammatical phenomenon and category must be taken into account.

Only a theory tested in practice can give complete knowledge. Therefore, grammatical phenomena should be studied not only in the system, but also in practice - in their application. In this case, one should not forget the important role of speakers in the creation of speech, as well as the role of the situation in the application and interpretation of grammatical phenomena [2,3].

Grammar studies specific language phenomena not only at the language-system level, but also at the level of speech and usage.

In language as an organized set of linguistic tools, two sides should be distinguished:

- system;
- structure;
- norm

A system is a whole set of elements, and a structure is a specific internal structure of this set. The concept of system pays special attention to the set of elements, the plurality. The structural-systemic study of the language phenomenon consists of:

- to determine the set of elements that make up the system, and for this, to separate them from similar phenomena, and to determine the set of these elements, and to separate them from similar phenomena, and to create principles that provide a basis for considering these elements as the same thing;

- specifies the determination of the existing internal relationships and connections between these elements, their hierarchical hierarchy and the ways in which one element is formed from another element. For example, when it comes to verb tenses in French, we need to determine how many and which units are included in this set of elements. That is why almost every section of theoretical grammar begins with this, that is, how many elements of this phenomenon are there in the language (such as how many articles, tenses, moods, proportions are there in French).

After the list of shapes is created, the relationship between them is determined by their organization. For example, three plans (epoques) - passé, present, future - are distinguished in the system of indicative tenses.

All other forms of the verb are distributed among these tenses. Then the opposite meanings of different forms are found (passé composé – passé simple, passé composé – imparfait, passé composé – plus-que parfait).

The concept of structure includes the relationship of form and content and shows it in each separately obtained form ((ill) parlait form is synthetic, (ill) a parle is defined as an analytical device).

A norm is a form of expression of a grammatical category stabilized in a certain language. An auxiliary verb in the past tense has the form of a past participle. However, the choice of which form of the verb and adjective is always based on the rules of the language: il a écrit, but il est venu (not a venu).

The developer can freely choose the elements of the system. But this choice is always subject to certain rules. Because the content of the thought changes accordingly. The noun in the sentence Jean appelle Pierre also changes (Pierre appelle Jean). Whether a word has a possessive or complement function depends on whether it comes before or after the verb. The elements of the norm are not optional, their use is mandatory and does not depend on the meaning. For example, in the given example, both nouns cannot be placed before or after the verb: Pierre Jean appelle not say, even if the meaning is clear: the French do not speak like that [4,5].

Neither the system nor the norm has an absolutely stable character. The instability of the system can be explained as follows: in order for language to be a perfect tool of communication, it must be organized in such a way that it is possible to express things and events that do not have a special sign. Therefore, words and categories should be flexible in content to the extent that it is possible to connect the concept they mean to the phenomenon of being.

The language system is asymmetrical. A stable system would have limited the use of language and complicated the choice of words and forms during communication.

Speech also has two aspects:

- general speech;
- individual speech.

The use of language forms in speech requires their selection, and sometimes their modification.

There are two types of elements in speech:

- individual aspect;
- non-individual, public element.

General speech is an important component of language activity, because knowing the forms and structures is not enough to master the language. It is also necessary to know the laws of their use in speech situations and contexts.

Grammar serves two purposes:

- laws of language construction
- studies the mechanisms of speech formation, i.e., the rules of selection of language elements - communication (communication - intervention, dialogue) units of thought formation.

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